

1 **Dlx5 controls Sox21 activation.**

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6 We demonstrate by depletion of Dlx5 in human cells that the Sox homeobox *Sox21* is a major molecular
7 target of *Dlx5*. The data point to a suggested theoretical entry point into transformation proper initiated
8 following activation of 'higher-order' Sox homeoboxes (e.g., *Sox2* and *Sox21*) by oncogenic homeoboxes
9 of the Dlx and Olig families controlled by the *Xist* non-coding RNA, upstream of *Pax8*, *Pbx1* and *Pbx2*, and
10 *Tgif2* activation.

11 Citations

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